

SSHOC-NL Socio-Economic History Community FAIR Implementation Report

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1. Introduction

Despite the wide endorsement of the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) on behalf of research institutions and funders, there is heterogeneity in the way the principles are implemented. While part of the variability in the implementation of the principles is desirable since FAIR is not “a” standard (Mons et al., 2017) and should reflect community needs, in practice, there has been a proliferation of standards and resources which are often not properly documented. FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) have been proposed as a solution to streamline the efforts of FAIR implementation (Maineri & Wang, 2022; Schultes et al., 2020): rather than leading to one, single, standard solution, FIPs encourage the documentation of community-specific FAIR strategies. The documentation effort contributes to enhancing transparency and makes it easier for communities to interoperate by design; it can also constitute a valuable self-reflection exercise for a community and help identify strengths and weaknesses in terms of FAIR implementation.

The FAIR Expertise Hub aims to support the creation of FAIR Implementation Profiles for Dutch communities in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), acting as a bridge across different communities and supplementing them with technical knowledge on FAIR when needed. The FIPs produced in this way actively contribute to creating a federated data infrastructure. In the report, we outline the FAIR Implementation Profile declared by the SSHOC-NL Socio-Economic History community (SEH in short in the remainder of this report). We subsequently compare it to FIPs from other communities and generate recommendations.

The SEH community consists of researchers and data experts in the Netherlands who conduct research and publish data about social history and economic history research. The members of the community come from different institutions and infrastructures, and in particular from the International Institute of Social History (IISG), Utrecht University (UU), and the Vrije Universiteit (VU) Amsterdam. Some members of the community also participate in the work programme of CLARIAH (the Dutch infrastructure for Digital Humanities) and ODISSEI (the Dutch infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Economics), which collaborate in the SSHOC-NL project. As the name suggests, the SEH community spans different disciplines from the SSH, as it combines interests and expertise on history and historical data sources with the socio-economic aspects, such as social inequalities and occupational dynamics. The key position of the community across the disciplines informs the choice of indicating SSHOC-NL in the community name: [SSHOC-NL](#) is a large infrastructure project funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and based on a collaboration between CLARIAH and ODISSEI (Dykstra et al., 2023). The FIP from the SEH community is a first step towards the inventory of FAIR implementation in the two infrastructures, casting light on similarities and differences across the communities in the two domains.

1.1. *Methodological note*

The core of the FIP hereby described has been developed during two virtual meetings, occurred in February 2023, with representatives from the community, and refined during further meetings and email exchanges over the course of the years. The tables report two versions of the endorsed FERs, 2023 and 2025, to show the improvements, changes, and

upgrades that SEH implemented and how they are captured by a FIP. Intermediate versions were not very well captured or documented. The “FIP Mini-questionnaire” [spreadsheet](#) has been used as a template for the FIP guidance questions and to record the answers and comments. Additionally, the data description part of some selected papers was reviewed in case of missing information (see Appendix B). Subsequently, members of the FAIR Expertise Hub have reported the answers into the FIP Wizard. Finally, we discuss the FIP with FAIR Assessment of selected datasets that are considered representative (see Appendix C).

2. The FAIR Implementation Community

2.1. *Description of the community*

The data produced, published, and (re)used by the communities is mostly in the form of tabular data, linked data, and geospatial data; the community is not often involved in the production of images, but images are sometimes (re)used. Recently, each FIP is restricted to one type of data. For this reason, there is no need to create other FIPs. Also, the data producers vary, spanning from archives, which underwent rapid digitalisation processes in the past decades, to individual researchers who create and publish data alongside “traditional” publications. Some data have been reported to be legacy data, or even worse, dark data. These data have been left out of the progress of the community’s FAIR effort. Moreover, the data handled in the community comes from various sources, such as:

- Physical objects held in museums and archives;
- Historical sources, such as: civil registries, population registries, tax records, provincial records, agricultural reports, historical CBS (Central Bureau of Statistics) publications, legal records from medieval times, almanacks, and historical newspapers¹.
- Structured vocabularies that have been co-developed by researchers from previous projects could be used to enrich metadata.

The users of the data in the community include researchers spanning across different disciplines, e.g., social scientists, evolutionary biologists, economists, historians, geneticists; also, genealogists (who are not necessarily researchers) are reported among the typical data users in the community.

Most recently, due to the special position and continuous effort on FAIR data management of this community, its metadata has been studied by secondary users. In the appendix is the FAIR assessment result (using FAIR Enough) of some representative datasets.

The SEH community also collaborates with other communities, which use different data types and sources. The following were indicated in particular:

- The Political History community, which makes more intensive use of videos, audio, and pictures;
- The Oral History community, which makes more intensive use of recordings;
- The Experimental Media Archaeology community, which deals with physical artefacts.

¹ Historical newspapers may offer an interesting use case to bridge to the Media Content Analysis Lab community.

2.2. Background participants

Beyond the data stewards employed at the university and research institutes who occasionally support researchers involved in the creation and reuse of data, there is no formal data steward in the community. The members of the community who participated in the meeting are researchers who are also experts in data stewardship and linked data approaches.

3. The FAIR Implementation Profile

3.1. Findability

Table 1 reports the overview of the FAIR resources for Findability declared by the community. In terms of Identifier types (F1), the declarations are in line with the most common PID services used in the SSH: the SEH community currently uses the Handle system to mint PIDs for datasets (see e.g., <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/MR4GPS> and <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/PCM0ZX>), ORCID for individuals, and DOIs for publications and other materials. It was mentioned that in the future, DOIs may be used for datasets. It follows from the choices declared in F1 that DOI and Universal handle resolver systems are used as metadata-data linking mechanism (F3).

In terms of Metadata schema (F2), in addition to the widespread DCAT and DDI, the community also declared the use of Encoded Archival Description (EAD) and machine-readable cataloguing (MARC21). These two standards are used due to specificity of the data sources used by the SEH community, since [EAD](#) is a standard (in XML) for describing archival resources, whereas [MARC21](#) is a standard (also in XML) for describing textual and audio-visual items in libraries' catalogues (e.g. books, music, maps, DVDs, other digital resources).

For what concerns the search engines (F4), the community prevalently uses the IISG Dataverse (they used DANS EASY in the past) to publish datasets and related metadata; however, in the future the IISG Dataverse will be replaced by DataverseNL. Metadata is also exposed to the Dutch Digital Heritage (NDE) Data register. Furthermore, the metadata is collected via the Dataverse API and sent to the ODISSEI Portal. It was, however, noted how different universities are adopting their own data repositories (e.g., from DataverseNL, Figshare, YODA), which might lead to having resources from the SEH community scattered across different repositories; hence, this is something that should be monitored in the future. Their use of different registries offers researchers different options for publishing data. It was noticed that Druid was developed by the community, but it is taken as an experimental setup rather than a community standard.

All in all, the community seems to be quite far along in terms of Findability (as indicated by the FAIR assessment scores reported above in Appendix A, where all datasets scored "Advanced" on the Findability metrics).

Table 1. FIP portion pertaining to the Findability principle.

FAIR principle	FAIR enabling resource types MD = metadata D = datasets	FERs endorsed (2023)	FERs endorsed (2025)
F1	Identifier service (MD)	DOI, Handle, ORCID	DOI, Handle, ORCID
F1	Identifier service (D)	DOI (to use), Handle	DOI (Future), Handle
F2	Metadata schema	MARC21, EAD, DDI, DCAT	MARC21, EAD3, DDI, DCAT2
F3	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	DOI, Universal Handle resolver system	DOI, Handle
F4	Registry (MD)	Dataverse, NDE network	IISG Dataverse (to be discontinued), NDE Dataregister, DataverseNL (Future)
F4	Registry (D)	Dataverse, [in the future: incorporated into DANS SSH data station]	IISG Dataverse (to be discontinued), DANS SSH data station (Future), DataversNL (Future), EASY (Past)

3.2. Accessibility

In terms of Accessibility, HTTPS, OAI-PMH, and REST APIs were indicated as chosen communication protocols for both data and metadata. As a metadata longevity plan, the community used to comply with the Core Trust Seal certification (see details of the CTS certification obtained by IISG [here](#)). However, it was noticed in later iterations that the CTS is not per se a metadata preservation policy. The preservation policy will be updated in future versions of the FIP when IISG's data management policy or code of conduct is published.

Note that the Accessibility level was marked as low by F-UJI, but this could be because the machine did not detect the access conditions from the metadata. This may be a problem embedded in the way Dataverse manages and exposes the metadata. In the Dataverse interface, the conditions can be read under the tab "Terms", where the information is provided for human readers.

It was noticed that the CTS is not a metadata preservation policy. Thus, the CTS was removed in this version. The preservation policy has not been published by the time this version was created.

Table 2. FIP portion pertaining to the Accessibility principle.

FAIR principle	FAIR enabling resource types MD = metadata D = datasets	FERs endorsed (2023)	FERs endorsed (2025)
A1.1	Communication protocol (MD)	OAI-PMH, HTTPS, REST API	OAI-PMH, HTTPS, REST API

A1.1	Communication protocol (D)	REST API, HTTPS, OAI-PMH	REST API, HTTPS, OAI-PMH
A1.2	Authentication & authorisation technique (MD)	HTTPS	HTTPS
A1.2	Authentication & authorisation technique (D)	SWORD; CLARIN AAI	SWORD; CLARIN AAI
A2	Metadata preservation policy	RDA CTS RDA Core Trust Seal Certification	None

3.3. Interoperability

In terms of Interoperability, the SEH community is quite advanced in their use of linked approaches. As knowledge representation languages (I1), RDF, XMLs, HTMLs are often used for representing both data and metadata. For data, Jinja (a web template engine for the Python programming language) was also indicated in 2023 but later removed

In terms of structured vocabularies for metadata (I2 MD), resources linked to the ones indicated for the metadata schemas in F2 are reported: EAD, MARC21, DCAT. For data, some discipline-specific resources are indicated. Interestingly, some of these vocabularies have been developed in projects that are part of or very close to the community:

- HISCO, the historical classification of occupations, which is also at the core of the History of Work project, briefly described in section 2;
- AMCO, the [AMsterdamse COde](#), a set of numeric codes used to identify municipalities over time (also used in the Historical Database of Dutch Municipalities);
- Historical ICD (H-ICD), or the Historical International Classification of Diseases;
- Vocabularies from the Intermediate Data Structure (IDS) for Longitudinal Historical Microdata (see next paragraph).

For metadata models (I3-MD) Intermediate Data Structure (IDS) for Longitudinal Historical Microdata (Alter & Mandemakers, 2014) is mentioned, whereas for data models (I3-D) no resource is in use, but there is a will to use Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL). [IDS](#) and [SHACL](#) are similar in scope, and specify validation schemas against which RDF graphs can be checked.

Jinja was removed from the FIP. It was taken as a templating technique instead. MARC21 is not repeated here but appears in the F2 part. The main changes are in I2 and I3 due to additional structured vocabularies found while revisiting the papers. They were not specified in the previous versions. This shows that it can be helpful to go through the corresponding papers while examining the community standards. PROV-O was added to I3.

Table 3. FIP portion pertaining to the Interoperability principle.

FAIR principle	FAIR enabling resource types MD = metadata D = datasets	FERs endorsed (2023)	FERs endorsed (2025)
11	Knowledge representation language (MD)	RDF (OWL, RDFS, etc.)	RDF (OWL, RDFS), SKOS
11	Knowledge representation language (D)	XML, HTML, RDF (same as above), Jinja	XML, HTML, RDF (RDFS, OWL)
12	Structured vocabularies (MD)	EAD, MARC21, DCAT	EAD, DCAT
12	Structured vocabularies (D)	HISCO, AMCO, Historical ICD (H-ICD), IDS	HISCO, AMCO, Historical ICD (H-ICD), IDS, HISCLASS, OCCSCORE, PRESGL, SEI, NPBOSS
13	Semantic model	IDS	IDS, PICO, schema.org (F), PROV-O (F)
13	Semantic model	SHACL (willing to use)	SHACL (F), BIO (F)

3.4. Reusability

In terms of Reusability, no community-specific resources are indicated. The default licence (R1.1) in the community is CC-BY-SA, and custom data use provisions are used for data that are under restricted access (e.g. HSN-DB)². DCAT is used as a provenance model (R1.2). PROV-O was added to R1.2 in the latest version. The default licence used to be CC0. The community decided to change it to CC-BY-SA to prevent the data from being given away or used for unintended purposes.

Table 4. FIP portion pertaining to the Reusability principle.

FAIR principle	FAIR enabling resource types MD = metadata D = datasets	FERs endorsed (2023)	FERs endorsed (2025)
R1.1	Data usage license (MD)	None	None
R1.1	Data usage license (D)	CC-BY-SA, CC0	CC-BY-NC, CC BY-SA 4.0 (default)
R1.2	Provenance model (MD)	DCAT	DCAT, PROV-O (F)
R1.2	Provenance model (D)	DCAT	DCAT

² The authors are not aware of a way to render custom licences in a machine-readable way.

4. FIP Use Cases

To prove that the FIP could be used to address the needs of data upcycling, there was a small study on the upcycling of legacy data. The results were captured in a workshop paper (see Appendix E). This paper is to be further expanded to a journal submission in the near future after some more detailed examination.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This report demonstrated how FIP can capture the community's decisions and be used to study changing decisions in a community regarding the use of resources that contribute to FAIR implementation in various aspects. As the community and the data management ecosystem evolve, the FAIR principle implementation could also change. Among the several FIPs for communities in the social sciences and humanities created in cooperation with the FAIR Expertise Hub, the SEH community has the most complete and mature profile compared to other communities. This is mostly due to the effort by Richard Zijdeman, Rick Mourits, and colleagues to increase the accessibility of data in their field.

The FIP methodology could be improved in future versions due to some drawbacks we noticed in this study. First of all, the relation between a community and the FERs does not capture resources used in the past. For example, EASY has been used in the past by the community, and thus it was created as a FER using the FIP wizard. However, it could not be associated to the community in the current design of the FIP due to a lack of the required relation in its ontology. At the moment, different versions of resources are considered different FERs. This could confuse automated convergence analysis. There was an update to the questions in the FIP template. Consequently, the answers have also been revised. In the updated template, the FIP methodology offers an assessment metric for each community regarding each type of its data. However, the (published) datasets are not specified. In addition, the previous FIP template suffered from having exactly one person as data steward. In reality, there could be more. After reporting to the developers of the FIP template, it has been fixed in time. The current design of FIP does not cover data format, which could be addressed in future versions. Finally, the FIP does not cover much about sustainability, transparency, and usability. Future FIP reports could be expanded to address issues such as the funding, the software used/created, scripts used for the curation and analysis of the data, examples, potential bias in the documentation, as well as documentation.

By the time this report is completed, the FIP addresses mostly tabular data. Given the change in the current design of FIP and the interdisciplinary nature of the field, another FIP might be needed to cover images or other types of data. Comparing the two versions of the FIPs, it was noticed that the community has not evolved much. Most changes refer to missing entries or incomplete reports of FERs. The FIP reflects how the community is relying on data repositories, e.g., the registration of PID and the use of Handle are provided by the data infrastructure (Dataverse), and the metadata schema used can be influenced by the options provided by the Dataverse.

The FIP reflects the community's continuous effort in making their data FAIR. Despite the need for maintaining published data, some attention should be given to legacy datasets and those that have been created in the past but not well maintained or published in the state-of-the-art data repositories. Some comparison with other communities and conversation with their data steward can be beneficial. Possible candidates include the CLARIN community, the ODISSEI Portal community, the DANS SSH Data Station community, and the GLOBALISE community. In addition, some conversation with the Belgian counterparts (i.e., research communities that conduct similar research using socio-economic data or historical data and related metadata schemas) could be beneficial for the interoperability. The FAIR Expertise Hub has taken some steps towards bridging the communities between these two countries, which could be followed up.

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Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018.
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Appendix A: Primitive FAIR Assessment using F-UJI

Prominent examples of data(sets) produced and published in the SEH community (with a preliminary FAIR assessment performed by a beta release of [F-UJI](#)³) include:

- The [Historical sample of the Netherlands](#) (HSN), a dataset including the individual life-courses (e.g., births, marriages, deaths) of 85,500 people born in the Netherlands between 1812 and 1922;
 - When scanned via F-UJI, the latest release of the dataset ([link](#)) gets a FAIR score of 43% or “Moderate”, broken down into an “Advanced” score on Findability, “Moderate” on interoperability, and “Initial” on Accessibility and Reusability.
- The [LINKing System \(LINKS\)](#), a system of linked civil certificates that enables the historical reconstruction of families;
 - When scanned via F-UJI, the latest release of the dataset ([link](#)) gets a FAIR score of 43% or “Moderate”, broken down into an “Advanced” score on Findability, “Moderate” on interoperability, and “Initial” on Accessibility and Reusability.
- The [Historical database for Dutch municipalities](#), linked data tracking municipalities over time, allowing continuity despite changes in names, borders, etc..
 - When scanned via F-UJI, the latest release of the dataset ([link](#)) gets a FAIR score of 62% or “Moderate”, broken down into an “Advanced” score on Findability and interoperability, “Moderate” on Accessibility and “Initial” on Reusability.
- The History of Work [occupational information system](#), tracking tens of thousands of occupational titles from countries and languages around the world from the sixteenth to the twentieth century, and mapping to standards such as the Historical-ISCO (HISCO).
 - When scanned via F-UJI, the latest release of the dataset ([link](#)) gets a FAIR score of 58% or “Moderate”, broken down into an “Advanced” score on Findability, “Moderate” on Interoperability, Accessibility, and Reusability.

Appendix B: Selected Papers Taken into Consideration While Reviewing FIP

1. Mourits, R., van Dijk, I. K., & Mandemakers, K. (2020). From Matched Certificates to Related Persons. *Historical Life Course Studies*, 9, 49-68.
<https://doi.org/10.51964/hlcs9310>

³ The test was performed on 28-04-2023.

2. Raad, J., Mourits, R., Rijpma, A., Schalk, R., Zijdeman, R., Mandemakers, K., & Meroño-Peñuela, A. (2020). Linking Dutch civil certificates. In A. Adamou, E. Daga, & A. Meroño-Peñuela (Eds.), WHiSe 2020 Workshop on Humanities in the Semantic Web 2020: Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Humanities in the Semantic Web (WHiSe 2020) co-located with 15th Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC 2020) Heraklion, Greece, June 2, 2020 (online) (pp. 47-58). (CEUR Workshop Proceedings; Vol. 2695). CEUR-WS. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2695/paper6.pdf>

Appendix C: FAIR Assessment of Representative Datasets using FAIR Enough

The following assessment was conducted using F-UJI on 30th Nov, 2023. Since no change has been made for these datasets and F-UJI has not been further developed, we keep these outdated results as they are for this FIP report. In case of any change, they will be updated in future versions. Below is the list of selected representative datasets:

1. LINKS family reconstitutions Zeeland: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/QUJNCD>
2. Historical Sample of the Netherlands: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/7ARQV2>
3. Historical Database Dutch Municipalities: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/RPBVK4>
4. Two datasets about the Historical Database of Suriname and the Caribbean at: <https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/dataverse/HDSC-HDC>. Their Handles are:
 - a) <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/1OV0RM>
 - b) <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/QKLHUV>
5. Historical atlas of the Low Countries: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/PGFYTM>
6. NLGIS boundary files with AMCO: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/URI8O2>
7. Labour conflicts in the Netherlands: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/APNT4U>
8. GLOBALISE VOC transcriptions: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/JCTCJ2>

Table 5. FAIR Assessment Results using F-UJI on Representative Datasets.

Aspect	Score	Dataset 1	Dataset 2	Dataset 3	Dataset 4a	Dataset 4b	Dataset 5	Dataset 6	Dataset 7	Dataset 8	Average
F	7	5.5	2.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	6	6	5.5	5.3
A	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1.2
I	4	2	0	3	2	2	3	2	2	2	2.0
R	10	3	0	4	2	4	4	5	5	4	3.4
Summary		47%	14%	56%	52%	52%	47%	62%	62%	52%	0.5

Other tools that can be used for similar assessments include [FAIR Enough](#) and [FAIR-Checker](#).

Appendix D: FERs added to the FIP Wizard

The following FERs have been created to complete this FIP: MARC21, EAD, IISG Dataverse, Dataverse, DataverseNL, NDE Dataset Register, DANS SSH Data Station, SWORD, JInja, HTML, EASY, H-ICO, HISCLASS, OCCSCORE, PRESGL, SEI, NPBOSS50.

Appendix E: Related Academic Publication

- Wang, S., Maineri, A., Singh, N.K., Kuhn, T. (2024). FAIR Implementation Profiles for Social Science. In: Garoufallou, E., Sartori, F. (eds) Metadata and Semantic Research. MTSR 2023. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 2048. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65990-4_26
- Wang, S., Maineri, A., Towards Rigorous Data Upcycling using the FAIR Implementation Profile for the SSHOC-NL Socio-Economic History Community, legacy4reuse - Criteria and Methods for Upcycling Data Collections in Social and Economic History, 2023. <https://shuai.ai/static/files/paper/upcycling.pdf>
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